

D5.6

List of Planned Participation in Events

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D5.6 List of planned participation in events

The DoA added a new deliverable to the ones already defined in the project proposal: D5.6. List of planned participation in events. According to the DoA, this Deliverable is an attachment to the DEC- plan¹ and therefore it is intimately linked to it. It will establish the means to encourage partners to identify their participation in the planned activities as defined in Table 6 of the DEC plan, ‘Targets for key dissemination activities’. Therefore, the main objective of this deliverable is to set out the strategy to report on the participation of the planned events, to monitor the dissemination activities linked to these events and make sure that it happens along the lines of the DEC Plan.

Table 1: Revision History

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	02 / 07 / 2021	FD, Usue Lorenz,	First draft with structure and content.
2.0	19/07/2021	KTU, Egle Butkeviciene	Reviewed version with comments
3.0	20 / 07 / 2021	FD, Usue Lorenz	Final version submitted

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¹ Canto-Farachala P., Lorenz, U., Franco, S., Brounéus, F., Norvoll, R. and Hummer, P. YouCount. D5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities. Zenodo. doi.10.5281/zenodo.4812107

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DoA	Document of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Work Package
YCS	Young citizen scientist

Executive Summary

The DoA added a new deliverable to the ones already defined in the project proposal: D.5.6. List of planned participation in events. According to the DoA, this Deliverable is an attachment to the DEC-plan and therefore it is intimately linked to it. It will establish the means to encourage partners to identify their participation in the planned activities as defined in Table 6 of the DEC plan, 'Targets for key dissemination activities'. Therefore, the main objective of this deliverable is to set out the strategy to report on the participation of the planned events, to monitor the dissemination activities linked to these events and make sure that it happens along the lines of the DEC Plan.

1 Introduction

YouCount's DEC strategy seeks to maximise the overall impact of the project and it sets out the dissemination strategy which aims at engaging with key citizen scientists and other stakeholders at the local, national and global levels to facilitate the scaling up of the project's main findings. Dissemination will be about making available the results of the project as soon as possible to a diverse set of stakeholders.

In this document, events are defined as a set of virtual or physical spaces in which the research team performs dissemination activities and engages in a dialogue around the project's results with YouCount's different target groups at various territorial levels (local, national, European). In section 6, the DEC Plan envisages the main type of activities foreseen for the deployment of the project's dissemination strategy, such as: publications, presentations, scientific sessions, trainings, conferences, etc. However, there is only a generic identification of the events that need to be concretised.

This deliverable aims at setting up a process of continuously tracking the events in which YouCount engages to set-up a dialogue with different stakeholders and at establishing a monitoring system that will allow the Consortium to define a strategic approach to the participation in events as defined earlier. It will inform both the DEC strategy and the Evaluation and impact assessment (WP4).

In the next section, we introduce YouPlan, which is the event planning and reporting tool of YouCount. The section includes the description and aims sought by the tool. The third section describes the process of having the tool updated and it explains how the tool is going to be used in YouCount as a reporting tool but also as a strategic tool.

2 YouPlan: Planning & Reporting Tool for Participation in Events

YouPlan is the planning and reporting tool for planning and tracking the foreseen participation in events. The tool has been designed in three building blocks (see Appendix A):

Block 1: List of planned events

It contains the generic list of events that are foreseen in the project

Block 2: Reporting

It contains two reporting forms:

- A - Reporting Planned events form: See Appendix B where the items included in the google form can be found.
- B- Reporting events (of the events held): See Appendix C where the items included in the google form can be found.

Block 3: Lists of reported planned and participation in events

This is a list that gathers all the event participation information entered in Block 2. It aims at making researchers aware of whether an event has already been reported or not, and it will help avoiding duplicate entries.

3. Process of planning and tracking the participation in planned events

As described before, events constitute ‘what’ the main dissemination activities take place (presentations, scientific sessions, national workshops, integration of formal education, etc.) and where the research team engages in a dialogue around the main results of YouCount with key stakeholders at the local, national and global levels.

The first step is to identify which of the dissemination activities are taking place in an event, in order to build the inventory of planned events. The dissemination activities presented in Table 3 below, are drawn from the DEC Plan’s Table 6 (Dissemination activities) and section 7.7 (General Public Events). Both capture the initial longlist of participation in events of the Consortium, but it needs to be reviewed to adopt a strategic approach regarding the main events in which YouCount should be represented, also facilitating a more efficient participation of the research team in the events.

Table 3. Inventory of Planned Participation in Events

	Type of activities	Target groups	Detailed description
1	Presentations	National and international conferences for the academic community in communication, sociology, social anthropology, social and community psychology, and social policy (N=22)	The proposed set of Conferences is detailed in table 6 of the DEC Plan.
2		Research council conferences/workshops	Participation in at least one conference arranged by the research councils in each country
3		National policy conferences/meetings	Presentation of YouCount results in one policy conference meeting in each country
4	Scientific sessions	Academic community (N=2)	Participation in the ECSA conference to present the YouCount project, participation in another relevant social science conference organising a scientific session
5	National workshops	Academic community and stakeholder groups	One in each country to present results, organized by Partners
6	Integration in formal education	Universities	Lectures on CSS and YouCount in relevant teaching courses and BA, MA and PhD level in science education and social policy/communication/ICT
7	LLs trainings and Forums	Local youths, stakeholders and policy makers	The results of the project will be made available to participants in

			the case studies on an ongoing basis
8	YouCount final conference	Policy makers at the European and local levels	A final conference will be organised at the end of the project in Brussels to present the results of the project

Source: Adapted from Table 6, Dissemination activities and section 7.7., General Public Events of the DEC Plan (Deliverable 5.7)

The list of planned participation in events contains eight different types of events that were initially identified as being interesting for the project. However, the consortium needs to think strategically about the identified events and reflect in which the consortium could jointly participate. Figure 1 illustrates a three step-logic process for planning and tracking partner’s participation in events. The process will be used to:

- Monitor and report to the European Commission on the participation in events.
- Analyse the strategic presence of YouCount in local, national and global events of different nature (with different stakeholders).
- Plan the participation in the most relevant events where the project’s results could be disseminated, specially encouraging joint collaborative dissemination initiatives among the consortium members and Young Citizen Scientists (YCS).

Figure 1. The Process of Tracking the Participation in Planned Events

1. Planning

Objective: Planned participation in events is reported periodically by the research teams, including the YCS. Each team is expected to reflect on the events in which YouCount should have presence at the local, national and global levels. It will allow the Consortium to conduct a strategic reflection on where to participate and also on the potential for joint collaboration.

How:

- The YouPlan monitoring system will allow the periodical reporting of the planned participation in events by the different research teams. Research teams’ members will be required to fill in Form number 2A, ‘Reporting Planned events - periodically (reporting periods)’- see Appendix A.
- The data compiled will be analysed and presented to reflect on the events in which YouCount should participate and on how to organize participation.

When:

- Reporting on the planned events will be required for every reporting period (periodically). This reflection will coincide with the internal and official reporting periods fixed by the Consortium and according to the calendar defined in the Appendix G of D6.1 Project Execution Handbook:

Table 4. Reporting Periods

Reporting period	Month – before:
1 At the submission of the deliverable	31 Jul, 2021
2 First Internal reporting	1 Dec, 2021
3 Mid-reporting period EC	1 Sep, 2022
4 Second Internal reporting	1 Jun, 2023
5 Final reporting EC	1 Mar, 2024

- The analysis derived from the data reported in YouPlan will be presented in the Consortium meetings every six months as defined in Appendix H of D6.1 Project

Execution Handbook. By presenting this analysis is meant to stimulate a debate on whether the Consortium is participating or not in the most relevant events or whether further actions should be taken to strengthen YouCount’s participation in events and if yes, how. Table 5 below, presents the schedule for the analysis.

Table 5. Time Schedule for the Reflection on the Participation in Events

Consortium Meeting	Month:
1 Consortium meeting	M8
2 Consortium meeting	M13
3 Consortium meeting	M17
4 Consortium meeting	M22
5 Consortium meeting	M26
6 Consortium meeting	M32

2. Reporting

Objective: continuous reporting on partners’ participation in events will be required together with evidence of participation.

How:

- Partners are expected to report on their participation in events as soon as possible after the event is celebrated.
- Partners will be required to fill in Form number 2B, ‘Reporting events - On a continuous basis (ongoing)’- see Appendix A.

When: project implementation phase.

3. Following-up

Objective:

- To monitor how the research team is performing regarding the objectives of planned participation in events and report to EB /GA / EC

How:

- The WP leader, FD (number 5), will present at the Consortium meeting how YouCount is meeting objectives.
- All the partners will report on their participation in events through the means provided.

When: in the Consortium meetings listed in Table 5 and together with the reflection based on the Planning of the participation in events

4. YouPlan: a tool in evolution

As defined in the DEC Plan, “In order to monitor the effectiveness of our DEC activities, YouCount will collect and monitor quantitative indicators and conduct qualitative measures from the target stakeholder groups. Partners will keep track of all YouCount communication, dissemination and exploitation activities other than standard social media and website interaction in a shared template that will be used for both monitoring and periodic reporting on DEC activities” (page 28, section 10).

Youplan will evolve to become YouCount’s Dissemination Activity Tracker allowing YouCount partners that carry out a specific action (i.e. press release, article, flyer, social media post, publication in their newsletter or website, writing scientific articles, etc.) to add a new entry on the tool including some basic information about the action and lessons learnt.

Appendixes

Table 6: Appendixes

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Appendix A. Screenshot of the Youplan's Main Page

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

YouPlan - the Planning & Reporting Tool for YouCount's Participation in Events

- 1** **Commitment with the EC**
Here you can find the **generic list of events** that are foreseen in the project: [Planned events](#)
- 2**
 - A** **Reporting Planned events - periodically (reporting periods)**
All YouCount partners, please add your participation in any **planned** events here: [Reporting Form Planned Events](#)
 - B** **Reporting events - On a continuous basis (ongoing)**
All YouCount partners, please add your participation in any **spontaneous** events here: [Reporting Form Events](#)
- 3** **Lists of planned and spontaneous participation in events**
In these sheets you will find all event participation information entered in the forms above. If you are unsure whether an event has already been reported or not, please consult these sheets before reporting it. This will help us avoid duplicate entries. [Reported Events](#)
[Reported Planned Events](#)

Appendix B. Reporting Planned Events Form

YouCount: Tracking form for reporting planned events 2021-2024

Dear YouCount partner,

Please fill in this reporting form whenever you participate in a planned event. Your input will be used for project reports sent to the European Commission.

If you are unsure whether the planned event has already been reported, please click on this link for a complete overview of all reported planned events: <https://bit.ly/3wNda7w>

If you wish to report a spontaneous event - please use this form instead:

E-mail address

Partner name

Type of event linked to (according to table 6 of the DEC Plan): [predescribed list?]

Name of the event:

Event start date:

Event end date:

Place where the event took place (eg. online, city, country)

Type of audience (as defined in table 3 of the DEC Plan)

- Academic community
- Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)
- Research councils and science communication institutions
- University institutions (formal education)
- Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations
- Young people (including YCS)
- General public
- Other, please specify:

Please describe briefly your participation in the event and the link to the YouCount project (presentation of results, of the project, conceptual discussion on issues related to the project, etc.)

Web link to YouCount's event material (if available)

Key learnings: anything you find interesting to share

Dissemination of YouCount's part(s) of the event:

Social media channels

- Newsletter and press release
- Non-scientific publication
- Media coverage
- Other, please specify:

Please provide link(s) and/or references to the dissemination (if available)

If you have any additional comments, please add them here:

Appendix C. Reporting Events Form

YouCount: Tracking form for reporting events 2021-2024

Dear YouCount partner,

Please fill in this reporting form whenever you have participated in an event. Your input will be used for project reports sent to the European Commission.

If you are unsure whether the planned event has already been reported, please click on this link for a complete overview of all reported planned events: <https://bit.ly/3wNda7w>

E-mail address

Partner name

Type of event linked to (according to table 6 of the DEC Plan):

Name of the event:

Event start date

Event end date

Place where the event took place (eg. Online, city, country)

Type of audience (as defined in table 3 of the DEC Plan)

- Academic community
- Other CS projects (i.e. Swafs Community)
- Research councils and science communication institutions
- University institutions (formal education)
- Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations
- Young people (including YCS)
- General public
- Other, please specify:

Please provide a brief description of your participation in the event and the link to the YouCount project (presentation of results, of the project, conceptual discussion on issues related to the project, etc.)

Web link to YouCount's event material (if available)

Key learnings: anything you find interesting to share

Dissemination of YouCount's part(s) of the event

- Social media channels
- Newsletter and press release
- Non-scientific publication
- Media coverage
- Other, please specify:

Please provide link(s) and/or references to the dissemination (if available)

If you have any additional comments, please add them here:

PARTNERS:

